

Role of TIPE Family of Proteins In the Development of Oral Squamous Cell Carcinoma

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Abstract:

Cancers of oral cavity is a major health concern worldwide with highest incidence in India. Unfortunately, in India, almost 2/3 of the oral cancer cases are diagnosed only in the advanced stage of the disease making it difficult to treat and decreasing the chances of survival. Therefore, it is essential to develop novel biomarkers for the better management of this deadly disease. In the current study, a novel tumor necrosis factor alpha induced protein 8 (TNFAIP8 or TIPE) protein family was examined for its therapeutic and prognostic potential against oral cancer. The protein family comprises of four proteins namely, TNFAIP8 (TIPE), TNFAIP8L1 (TIPE1), TNFAIP8L2 (TIPE2) and TNFAIP8L3 (TIPE3). Immunohistochemical analysis revealed that expression of TIPE, TIPE2 and TIPE3 were upregulated and levels of TIPE1 were downregulated in squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) tissues compared to the normal tissues. In addition, treatment of oral cancer cells with tobacco and related carcinogens resulted in a significant upregulation of TIPE, TIPE2 and TIPE3 and downregulation of TIPE1 protein. Moreover, knockout of TIPE proteins was found to modulate the cancer hallmarks associated with oral cancer such as cancer cell survival, proliferation, colony formation and migration. Further, while TIPE, TIPE1 and TIPE2 proteins exhibited their activity through regulation of Akt/mTOR signaling cascade, TIPE3 acted through an Akt-independent mTOR/STAT3 pathway. Taken together, our results suggest that the TIPE proteins can be used as drug targets for the treatment of oral cancer.

Keywords:

TIPE, TIPE 1, TIPE2, TIPE3, oral cancer

References:

1. Bordoloi D, Banik K, Shabnam B, Padmavathi G, Monisha J, Arfuso F, Dharmarajan A, Mao X, Lim LHK, Wang L, Fan L, Hui KM, Kumar AP, Sethi G, Kunnumakkara AB. TIPE Family of Proteins and Its Implications in Different Chronic Diseases. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2018 Sep 29;19(10).
2. Padmavathi G, Banik K, Monisha J, Bordoloi D, Shabnam B, Arfuso F, Sethi G, Fan L, Kunnumakkara AB. Novel tumor necrosis factor- α induced protein eight (TNFAIP8/TIPE) family: Functions and downstream targets involved in cancer progression. *Cancer Lett.* 2018 Sep 28;432:260-271.

Activation of Wnt antagonism mediates the antitumor activity and chemosensitizes breast cancer stem-like cells to ursolic acid, a pentacyclic triterpenoid

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Abstract:

Breast cancer is the most commonly diagnosed cancer and second leading cause of cancer death in women. Cancer metastasis, resistance and recurrence hinders successful treatment for breast cancer. Identification of breast cancer stem cells as the chemoresistant and tumor initiating population represents an important milestone in approaching anticancer therapies. Targeting this minor subpopulation of chemo- and radioresistant stem-like cells, termed as the cancer stem cells (CSCs) and their ultimate eradication could significantly enhance clinical outcomes. CSCs are resistant to conventional cytotoxic agent and radiology therapy. They also display aggressive invasion phenotype. Cancer stem cells share core signaling pathways with normal somatic stem cells, but also exhibit distinctions that provide important clues into useful therapeutic targets. Aberrant regulation of Wnt signalling by autocrine mechanism is reported which promote the CSC proliferation and survival from the chemotherapy. In this study we observed that ursolic acid, a natural compound derived pentacyclic triterpenoid, had a potent inhibitory effect on breast cancer cells by not only inducing apoptosis but also by reducing the stemness properties and decreasing the CSC population. As self-renewal and chemoresistant properties of CSCs are linked to the Wnt β -catenin pathway, we hypothesized that the observed effects of these compounds on CSC could be through modulating this pathway. Our results clearly suggests that plant derived compounds like UA are capable of targeting cancer stem cells and exert their effect by antagonizing the Wnt- β -catenin pathway.

Keywords:

Cancer stem cells, Breast cancer , antitumor, ursolic acid, triterpenoid

The innovation and new technology in healthcare, including Virtual Reality, Artificial Intelligence, Augmented Reality and Artificial Intelligence

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Abstract:

Healthcare is fast shifting towards the digital age, with all stakeholders rushing to join the digital era. As major players in the healthcare industry, pharmaceutical companies are not spared the rush. Due to various factors, the pharmaceutical stakeholders have been hesitant in investing in technology, which would drastically change the delivery of healthcare products.

Compared to many other industries, pharmaceutical production undergoes demanding regulations. Changes to production mean changes to the machines, processes and ultimately the product itself.

Humans, machines, processes and IT. In the factory of the future, everything and everyone is connected therefore it is important for industry players to integrate digital healthcare technologies into its services. There are countless possibilities for our industry to utilize digital healthcare technologies, like integrating it into a smart phone application, having a virtual reality device for training and to detect and profile precision pain management.

On the priority list is the importance of tumour profiling in difficult-to-treat tumours. Some cancers, as we know, are complicated. Treatment for these tumours are not straightforward and in the past, these patients may have to go through trial and error to see which therapy works in them. The situation is far from ideal and the one suffering the most is the patient, whose quality of life is negatively affected by survival of the patient, as we know, earlier treatment often brings about better outcomes. The company has now extended its profiling to include exome and transcriptome. While the information garnered from exome and transcriptome profiling has no clinical impact at this point, the information may come in handy in the near future, as research in the field of tumour treatment continues to develop at a rapid rate.

Keywords:

Virtual reality, artificial intelligence, augmented reality, tumor profiling, Caris Life Science, digital healthcare technology.

Figure 1: Deploying Augmented Reality to "Breatherite" Breatherite is an inhaler-agonistic smartphone app that incorporates augmented reality (AR) technology to address historically poor inhaler technique across the world to help Asthma sufferers achieve greater control of their medical treatment.

References:

Mundipharma

Improving Cancer Diagnostics using an empirical assay for assessing Genomic Sensitivity

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Abstract:

Despite detection tests being developed for many cancers, there is no single test to identify cancer in general. We have developed such an assay. In this modified patented Comet assay, we investigated peripheral lymphocytes of 208 individuals: 20 melanoma, 34 colon cancer, 4 lung cancer patients 18 suspect melanoma, 28 polyposis, 10 COPD patients and 94 healthy volunteers. The natural logarithm of the Olive tail moment was plotted for exposure to UVA through different agar depths for each of the above groups and analysed using a repeated measures regression model. Response patterns for cancer patients formed a plateau after treating with UVA where intensity varied with different agar depths. In comparison, response patterns for healthy individuals returned towards control values and for pre/suspected cancers, were intermediate with less of a plateau. All cancers tested exhibited comparable responses. Analyses of Receiver Operating Characteristic curves, of mean log Olive tail moments, for all cancers plus pre/suspected-cancer versus controls gave a value for the area under the curve of 0.87; for cancer versus pre/suspected-cancer plus controls the value was 0.89; and for cancer alone versus controls alone (excluding pre/suspected-cancer), the value was 0.93. By varying the threshold for test positivity, its sensitivity or specificity can approach 100% whilst maintaining acceptable complementary measures. Evidence presented indicates that this modified assay shows promise as both a stand-alone test and as a possible adjunct to other investigative procedures, as part of detection programmes for a range of cancers. This test has been repeated with 900 individuals and responses remain equally predictive.

Keywords:

Cancer Diagnostics

Figure 1. The Comet assay procedure.

Figure 2. Mean log of the OTMs (95% CI) against lymphocyte depth in the gel for all groups. In patients with cancer, a plateau formed after treating with UVA, across doses represented at 3–4 different depths of agar.

Biography :

Professor Anderson (H index 63) holds the Established Chair in Biomedical Sciences at the University of Bradford, UK. She obtained her first degree in the University of Wales and second degrees in the Faculty of Medicine, University of Manchester. She has 500+ peer-reviewed papers, 9 books, has successfully supervised 32 PhDs, is an editorial board member of 10 international journals. She is Editor-in-Chief of a book Series on Toxicology for the Royal Society of Chemistry. She gives key note addresses at various international meetings. She is a consultant for many international organisations, including WHO, EU, NATO, TWAS, UNIDO, OECD